

Solid phase extraction of Hg^{II} ions with cross-linked poly(acrylic acid), coated on silanized silica gel

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Abstract : A selective and reliable method has been developed for the extraction and separation of Hg^{II} with high molecular mass cross-linked poly(acrylic acid) coated on silanized silica gel. The coated material acts as stationary phase for the extraction. Ion exchange and break-through capacity of the exchanger have been measured. The optimum pH range for the quantitative extraction of Hg^{II} was found to be 5.0–6.0. The elution behaviors of Hg^{II} have been investigated. A plausible mechanism for Hg^{II} extraction and elution has been suggested. Hg^{II} has been isolated quantitatively from various synthetic mixtures containing heavy metal ions (Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Cu²⁺).

Keywords : Cross-linked poly(acrylic acid), silanized silica gel, ion exchange, solid-phase extraction.

Introduction

There are many removal methods available for mercury such as solvent extraction, ion exchange, electrochemical precipitation, adsorption, etc¹. However, metal ion adsorption onto solid polymer surface (Solid phase extraction, SPE) is now considered as one of the most promising techniques for concentration, removal and recovery of metal ions from wide variety of sources due to eco-friendliness, fastness, simplicity and cost effectiveness. The selectivity of these materials towards metal ion can be controlled by the immobilized functional group, pH of the medium, presence of masking agents, temperature, etc. The polymeric matrix affects other properties, namely the ion-exchange capacity, kinetic features, mechanical and chemical strength and regeneration.

In the present decade, several researchers are engaged in synthesizing suitable polymers having selective metal ion binding capacity^{1,2}. Very few of them deal with the removal and recovery of mercury ion from aqueous solution^{1,2}. The cross-linked poly(acrylic acid) coated on silanized silica gel is reported to be good extractor for lead(II), iron(III), cerium(IV) and uranium(VI)³. The structural features of the developed exchanger are suitable for the extraction of Hg^{II}.

The present article reports the systematic studies on

solid-phase extraction of Hg^{II} and its separation from synthetic mixtures containing metal ions (Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}) commonly found in ores, alloys and industrial wastewater using cross-linked poly(acrylic acid) coated on silanized silica gel.

Results and discussion

Physico-chemical characteristics of the ion-exchanger :
The exchange capacity of the prepared exchanger was determined at 25 °C and found to be 2.52 meq H⁺ g⁻¹. The value is superior to the literature values (1.90–1.96 meq H⁺ g⁻¹) of commercially available carboxylic resins such as *n*-capric acid and SRS-100⁴. The break-through capacity of both the dry exchanger (polymer coated silica) and polymer were measured and the values were 39.60 and 275 mg of Hg^{II} per g respectively at pH 5.5 at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. At the flow rate of 1 mL/min, 7.92% of the available carboxylic acid (1.5 × 10²¹ per g of resin) was used to bind mercury (HgAc⁺). Break-through capacity was increased with the decrease of flow rate and increase of pH (Fig. 1). The weight (D_g) and bed (D_v) distribution coefficients of the developed exchanger were calculated from break-through curves (Fig. 1) using the eqs. (1) and (2) and the results are shown in Table 1⁵.

Fig. 1. The break-through curves of Hg^{II} in the aqueous medium at different pH and flow rates (c = concentration of Hg^{II} in the effluent; c_0 = concentration of Hg^{II} in the influent = 2.20 mg/mL): (a) pH 5, flow rate 5 cm³/min, (b) pH 5, flow rate 1 cm³/min, (c) pH 5.5, flow rate 5 cm³/min, (d) pH 5.5, flow rate 1 cm³/min.

Table 1. The values of the weight (D_g) and bed (D_v) distribution coefficients of Hg^{II} in aqueous system at different pH and flow rates

Curves	pH	Flow rate (mL/min)	D_g (cm ³ /g)	D_v
a	5.0	5	10.872	0.787
b	5.0	1	16.072	1.057
c	5.5	5	18.872	1.097
d	5.5	1	21.572	1.198

The table shows that both the distribution coefficients were increased with increase of pH (from 5 to 5.5) and decrease of flow rate (from 5 to 1 mL/min).

$$D_g = \frac{U - U_0 - V}{m_j} \quad (1)$$

$$D_v = \frac{U - U_0 - V}{V_j} \quad (2)$$

where, U = volume (cm³) of the effluent at $c = c_0/2$ (determined graphically); U_0 = the resin dead volume (cm³); V = inter particle void of the ion exchanger (cm³) (which amounts to ca. 0.4 of U_0); m_j = weight (g) of the dry exchanger; V_j = volume (cm³) of the effluent at the break-through point.

Effect of pH on Hg^{II} retention and extraction mechanism: The retention of Hg^{II} was studied within the pH range 2.5–7.0 (Fig. 2) using 0.1 M acetate buffer. The retention (mg/g) increases with the increase of pH, reaches a maximum at 5.5 and then decreases with further in-

Fig. 2. Retention of Hg^{II} at different pH [flow rate = 1.0 mL/min; column : 0.8 cm × 8 cm].

crease of pH. The quantitative extraction of Hg^{II} was found around pH 5.0–6.0.

In acetate buffer medium (pH = 5–6), the mercury ion remains in equilibrium mainly as acetate complex (eq. (3))⁶. Having suitable size and charge, the species (HgAc⁺) probably goes to the exchange site as per following suggested path (eq. (4)). The high exchange capacity (2.52 meq H⁺/g) of the materials favours the ion exchange process. The absence of sharp peak at 1700 cm⁻¹ and appearance of a new peak at 1595 cm⁻¹ in the FTIR spectrum (Fig. 3) of Hg^{II} adsorbed exchanger clearly indicates the presence of carboxylate anion in the metal loaded sample⁷.

At low pH (<4.5), the equilibrium (eq. (4)) shifts to-

Fig. 3. FTIR spectrum of Hg^{II} ion loaded exchanger.

wards left. As a result, quantitative extraction of Hg^{II} did not take place in this condition. The metal ion passed out with the mobile phase as soluble mercury acetate at pH ≤ 3. While at high pH (> 6.5), the mercury ion undergoes hydrolysis and interfere the exchange process (eq. (4)).

The systematic studies on stripping gave the quantitative elution of Hg^{II} with HNO₃ (≥ 0.1 M), H₂SO₄ (≥ 0.05 M), HCl (≥ 0.05 M), CH₃COOH (≥ 0.1 M) and HClO₄ (≥ 0.1 M) (Table 2). The stripping (elution) follows the

Table 2. Effect of stripping agents on the extraction of Hg^{II}

Eluents	Concentration (M)	V _{max} (mL)	V _t (mL)	Recovery (%)
HNO ₃	0.005	–	110	0
	0.01	60	100	11.84
	0.05	55	100	75.60
	0.1	35	60	99.60
CH ₃ COOH	0.01	–	100	0
	0.05	–	70	0
	0.1	20	40	99.20
H ₂ SO ₄	0.01	–	100	0
	0.05	35	60	99.50
	0.1	20	40	99.70
HCl	0.05	30	60	98.89
	0.1	12	25	99.57
HClO ₄	0.05	50	90	93.63
	0.1	17	40	99.50
	0.5	5	9	99.65

[Hg^{II} taken = 2.20 mg; column : i.d. 0.8 cm, bed height 8 cm; flow rate = 1.0 mL min⁻¹; pH = 5.5; temperature = 25 °C].

reverse path of extraction (eq. (4)). Thus, organic acid (CH₃COOH), being weak electrolyte is less efficient than that of inorganic acids used. Among inorganic acids, HNO₃ and HClO₄ are less active compared to HCl and H₂SO₄, due to their lower complex formation ability. The complex formation ability of different anions with Hg^{II} follows the order : Cl⁻ > SO₄²⁻ >> ClO₄⁻ > NO₃⁻. Thus H₂SO₄ and HCl having molarities greater or equal to 0.05 were found to be suitable eluent for Hg^{II}. The elution of diverse metal ions has been carried out with different acids. It was found that Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} were stripped quantitatively with both 0.005 M H₂SO₄ and 0.005 M HNO₃. While Pb^{II} was eluted with 0.01 M HNO₃ satisfactorily. These eluents were used throughout the experiments. The requirement of different acids for stripping various diverse metal ions may be attributed to the differences in interaction between metal ion and exchanger. Stronger interaction requires higher acid concentration for qualitative elution of that metal ion.

The pH of the exchanger was adjusted at 5.5. Then 10 mL Hg²⁺ (0.013–0.0067 mg mL⁻¹) was mixed with 10 mL buffer at desired pH and passed through the column at optimum flow rate of 1 mL/min. During ten successive loading, mercury ions have been accumulated gradually on the resin bed and the column was washed thoroughly with double distilled water. Then extracted ions were stripped with 0.1 M HCl. The pre-concentration factor (PF) with subsequent recovery of Hg^{II} (Table 3) indicates a high degree of extraction and recovery of Hg^{II}. In this process the recovery and pre-concentration factor were found to be 97.01–98.07% and 7.76–7.85 respectively.

Table 3. Pre-concentration and recovery of mercury ions

Volume of mercury ion solution passed (mL)	Initial concentration of mercury ion (mg/mL), C_i	Volume of 0.1 M HCl (mL) required for elution	Concentration of mercury ion in the effluent (mg/mL), C_f (Average of three determinations)	P.F. ^a (C_i/C_f)
200	0.0130	25	0.102	7.85
200	0.0067	25	0.052	7.76

[Flow rate = 1.0 mL/min; pH = 5.5; column : i.d. 0.8 cm, bed height 8 cm; temperature = 25 °C; ^apre-concentration factor].

Method of Hg^{II} separation from binary mixtures : It was possible to separate Hg^{II} from several metal ions present in binary mixture by using selective stripping agents. Each binary mixture was prepared by mixing an aliquot of standard solution of Hg^{II} (2.20 mg mL⁻¹) and one of the diverse metal ions in acetate buffer at desired pH (A to F, Table 4). At pH 5.5, Cu^{II}, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cd^{II} were co-extracted quantitatively along with Hg^{II} from their respective binary mixtures (A to F). Hg^{II} was eluted first from the column with the help of 0.05 M H₂SO₄ for the mixture A, and when Pb^{II} was eluted with 0.01 M HNO₃. Diverse metal ions Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} which belonged to the mixtures of B, C, D and E

respectively were eluted first with 0.005 M H₂SO₄, leaving behind Hg^{II} in the column. Cd^{II} of mixture F (Hg^{II}/Cd^{II}) was stripped first with 0.005 M HNO₃ keeping Hg^{II} in the resin bed. Later, Hg^{II} ions were eluted from the respective column using 0.05 M H₂SO₄ (B to F). Required volume of each eluents is given in the Table 4. After recovery, metal ions were determined complexometrically⁸.

In order to assess the possible analytical applications, the proposed method was applied to separate Hg^{II} from multi-component synthetic mixtures containing mercury with different metal ions commonly associated industrial samples and belong in same analytical group (G to H of Table 4). A clean separation of Hg^{II} from ternary syn-

Table 4. Separations of Hg^{II} from synthetic metal ion mixtures

Mixtures	Cations	Added (mg)	Recovered (mg)	RSD (%)	Eluent (M) (mL)
A	Hg ^{II}	2.20	2.22	3.73	0.050 H ₂ SO ₄ , (60)
	Pb ^{II}	2.15	2.17	3.22	0.010 HNO ₃ , (50)
B	Hg ^{II}	2.20	2.18	3.80	0.050 H ₂ SO ₄ , (60)
	Cu ^{II}	2.85	2.90	1.69	0.005 H ₂ SO ₄ , (50)
C	Hg ^{II}	2.20	2.22	2.61	0.050 H ₂ SO ₄ , (60)
	Co ^{II}	2.50	2.52	1.03	0.005 H ₂ SO ₄ , (30)
D	Hg ^{II}	2.20	2.22	1.98	0.050 H ₂ SO ₄ , (60)
	Ni ^{II}	2.15	2.12	1.50	0.005 H ₂ SO ₄ , (40)
E	Hg ^{II}	2.20	2.21	3.48	0.050 H ₂ SO ₄ , (60)
	Zn ^{II}	2.63	2.62	2.17	0.005 H ₂ SO ₄ , (45)
F	Hg ^{II}	2.20	2.18	2.02	0.050 H ₂ SO ₄ , (60)
	Cd ^{II}	1.80	1.83	3.87	0.005 HNO ₃ , (50)
G	Hg ^{II}	2.20	2.16	2.50	0.050 H ₂ SO ₄ , (60)
	Cu ^{II}	2.85	2.87	1.74	0.005 H ₂ SO ₄ , (50)
	Pb ^{II}	2.15	2.13	2.51	0.010 HNO ₃ , (50)
H	Hg ^{II}	2.20	2.24	2.41	0.050 H ₂ SO ₄ , (60)
	Cd ^{II}	1.80	1.78	1.78	0.005 HNO ₃ , (50)
	Zn ^{II}	2.63	2.65	1.50	0.005 H ₂ SO ₄ , (45)

[Column : i.d. 0.8 cm, bed height 8 cm, flow rate = 1.0 mL min⁻¹; pH = 5.5; temperature = 25 °C; RSD = relative standard deviation].

thetic mixture (H) is exhibited by a representative elution curve (Fig. 4). Results show high degree of effectiveness and utility of the proposed method.

Fig. 4. Elution profile of Hg^{II}, Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} mixture.

Experimental

Acrylic acid (Qualigens fine chemicals, Mumbai, India), sodium lauryl sulphate (Glaxo, Mumbai, India), *N,N'*-methylene bisacrylamide (Fluka, Buchs, Switzerland), ammonium persulphate (S.D. Fine Chem. Ltd., Boisar, India), mercuric nitrate (Sarabhai M. Chemicals, Baroda, India), dimethyl dichlorosilane (Merck, Mumbai, India), sodium acetate (Qualigens fine chemicals, Mumbai, India), acetic acid (Merck, Mumbai, India), hexamine (S.D. Fine Chem. Ltd., Boisar, India), xylenol orange (S.D. Fine Chem. Ltd., Boisar, India) and methanol (Bengal Chemicals, Mumbai, India) were used as received. An Elico LI 120 pH meter, thermostat and chromatographic column (i.d. 0.8 cm, Borosil) were also used.

Acrylic acid (1 mL), distilled water (10 mL) and sodium lauryl sulphate (1 g) were taken in a three-necked round bottom flask that was kept in a constant temperature (70 °C) water bath and mixed well by a magnetic stirrer. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the solution at least for 30 min to create inert atmosphere. *N,N'*-Methylene-bis-acrylamide (0.5 g) and ammonium persulphate (1 g) were then added as described earlier and stirred. After two hours the precipitated white polymer was filtered, washed with distilled water and dried under vacuum until constant weight. The characterization of the polymer was already reported³.

Silica gel (25 g) was rendered hydrophobic by exposing it to the vapour of dimethyl dichlorosilane (2.5 mL) in nitrogen atmosphere to make it inert support. The dimethyl dichlorosilane treated (silanized) silica gel was then washed with anhydrous methanol and dried at 100 °C

to a constant weight. It was then impregnated with 18% (w/v) polymer solution in benzene and dried in a rotary vacuum evaporator to achieve uniform coating. The exchanger was washed with distilled water and dried. Ion exchange bed was prepared by usual method⁴. The chemistry of silanization and immobilization were discussed in details earlier³.

General extraction procedure : The prepared ion exchanger was loaded in the chromatographic column (i.d. 0.8 cm) to achieve a bed height of 8 cm and then it was washed with 2 M HCl to remove excess organic solvent. An aliquot of metal ions in acetate buffer was passed through the column (pre-adjusted pH 5.5) at a flow rate of 1.0 mL per min. After extraction (retention) of metal ions, it was eluted (stripped) with suitable eluent (stripping agent). The amount of metal ion in each fraction of effluent was determined complexometrically⁸.

Conclusions :

The proposed method is simple, rapid, selective and economic. It needs only 2.5 h for complete separation and estimation. It was found that exchanger bed could be used more than 40 cycles with its full exchange capacity. The exchange and break-through capacity of the prepared cation exchanger are considerably higher than the commercially available Versatic-10, SRS-100 and *n*-capric acid. The developed exchanger functions well in the temperature range 20–40 °C and pH range 5.0–6.0 with respect to Hg^{II}. Both H₂SO₄ and HCl were used as selective stripping agent for the separation of Hg^{II}. Clear separation of Hg^{II} have been achieved from several toxic and heavy metal ions such as Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II}.

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